

LUT Moodle Towards Sustainable Digital Education: Designing User-Centred Platforms for Environmental Awareness and Behaviour Change.

Lappeenranta–Lahti University of Technology LUT

School of Engineering Science

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ABSTRACT

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Sustainability has become a global priority to ensure a balanced future for humanity and the environment. E-learning platforms can raise awareness and bring meaningful change. This study investigates Moodle's user experience and how sustainability awareness may be incorporated to support sustainable practices and raise environmental awareness. Although Moodle promotes sustainability by lowering travel emissions and dependence on physical resources, it still needs features that actively raise sustainability awareness. This study followed a user-centred design approach to make the platform more engaging and promote sustainability. Data was gathered using qualitative interviews with open-ended questions and quantitative surveys with closed-ended questions. The proposed design elements, such as Doodle of the Day, quizzes, and reward badges, are intended to increase interaction and encourage adopting sustainable habits. Based on the data analysis, personas and journey maps were also made.

The findings show that UCD can make Moodle an effective tool for teaching sustainability. Most students were optimistic about incorporating sustainability content into Moodle, with 85.8% indicating they were more likely to adopt sustainable practices after engaging with interactive materials. However, there are limitations. The study only looked at a narrow group of LUT University users; therefore, its broader relevance must be tested in other universities. The long-term impact on knowledge and motivation for sustainability needs to be explored. So, there are opportunities for further research.

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DECLARATION OF AI USAGE

This study acknowledges that artificial intelligence tools were used during its development. Specifically, the Grammarly grammar checker was used to improve clarity and coherence. ChatGPT- 4 (OpenAI) and Grammarly were utilised to assist in the following task:

Grammar Assistance: AI writing assistants helped refine the text, making it clearer and more cohesive while ensuring it followed proper grammar and style.

I take complete responsibility for the content of this thesis work and confirm that it follows the highest standards of ethical research practices.

ABBREVIATIONS

LUT - Lappeenranta University of Technology (LUT)

LMS – Learning Management System

Moodle – E-learning platform used in LUT university

LCA – Life Cycle Analysis

UCD – User-Centred Design

UX - User Experience

E-learning - Electronic Learning

PHP - PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor

CMS – Content Management System

LTI - Learning Tools Interoperability

HTML – Hypertext markup language

OECD - Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development

IUCN - International Union for Conservation of Nature

UN - United Nations

EFS - Education for Sustainability

SIE - Sustainability in Education

UNESCO - United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

RSS - Really Simple Syndication

WWF - World Wildlife Fund

PDFs - Portable Document Format

AI - Artificial Intelligence

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT

(ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS)

(DECLARATION OF AI USAGE)

(ABBREVIATIONS)

1	Introduction	18
1.1	Background	18
1.2	Purpose of the Study	19
1.3	Structure of the Thesis	19
2	Research Questions	21
3	Literature Review	21
3.1	Digital Education	21
3.2	Moodle	24
3.3	Sustainability	26
3.4	User-Centred Design.....	29
4	Research Methodology	31
4.1	Case Study on Existing LUT Moodle	32
4.2	Surveys.....	32
4.2.1	Survey on Existing LUT Moodle:	33
4.2.2	Survey on Proposed Frameworks:	33
4.3	Interviews.....	33
4.4	Ethical Data Collection	34
4.4.1	Surveys.....	34
4.4.2	Interviews.....	34
5	Results	35
5.1	Case Study on Existing LUT Moodle	35
5.1.1	User-Centred Design.....	35
5.1.1.1	Login Page	35

5.1.1.2	Dashboard Page	38
5.1.1.3	Course page.....	43
5.1.2	Sustainability Assessment.....	44
5.1.2.1	Environmental Impact.....	44
5.1.2.2	Social Impact	45
5.1.2.3	Economic Impact	45
5.1.3	Sustainability in Learning and Behaviour	46
5.1.4	Life Cycle Analysis (LCA).....	46
5.1	Results from Quantitative Data Analysis.....	47
5.2	Results from Qualitative Data Analysis.....	54
5.3	Results from Proposed Design Data Analysis	56
6	Discussion.....	59
6.1	Interpretation of Results.....	59
6.2	Comparison with Existing Literature.....	60
6.3	Implications of the Findings	61
6.4	Limitations of the Study	62
6.5	Recommendations for Future Research	62
7	Proposed Design.....	63
7.1	Components	64
7.2	Implementation Strategies	68
8	Summary.....	71
9	References	73

Appendices

Appendix 1. Questionnaires of Survey on Existing LUT Moodle

Appendix 2. Questionnaires of Interview on Existing LUT Moodle

Appendix 3. Questionnaires of Survey on Proposed Design

Appendix 4. Responses to Survey on Proposed Design

Appendix 5. The GitHub repository links to the prototype page

Appendix 6. Miro board link for Persona

Appendix 7. Miro board link for Journey map

Figures

Diagram 1: Structure of Thesis

Diagram 2: Research Methodology

Figure 1: Login Page

Figure 2: 2-way verification

Figure 3: Dashboard

Figure 4: Blocks in Dashboard

Figure 5: Calender Block

Figure 6: Completion Progress Block

Figure 7: Course Overview Block

Figure 8: Latest Badges

Figure 9: Recently access courses block

Figure 10: Tags Block

Figure 11: Course Page

Figure 12: Proposed Framework Components

Figure 13: Proposed Dashboard

Figure 14: Proposed course Dashboard

Figure 15: Proposed Quiz

Figure 16: Proposed Badge reward

Figure 17: Persona of Zohora

Figure 18: Journey map of Zohora

Figure 19: Survey on Existing LUT Moodle

Figure 20: Survey on Proposed Design

Figure 21: Engagement and Interest in the "Doodle of the Day"

Figure 22: Likelihood of Regular Interaction with the "Doodle of the Day"

Figure 23: Effectiveness of Quizzes in Testing Sustainability Concepts

Figure 24: Impact of Earning Badges on Future Interaction with Sustainability Features

Figure 25: Overall Satisfaction with These Features (Doodles, Quizzes, Badges)

Figure 26: Ease of Navigation and Usability (Survey)

Figure 27: Importance of Sustainability-Related Content

Figure 28: Preferred Types of Sustainability-Related Content

Figure 29: Likelihood to Adopt Sustainable Practices

Figure 30: Impact of a User-Friendly Design on Engagement

Figure 31: Interest in Sustainability-Related Content

Figure 32: Perceived Engagement Level with Sustainability-Related Content

Figure 33: Challenges in using LUT Moodle

Figure 34: Importance of Sustainability Features in Concern of Usability

Figure 35: Key Aspects of UCD for Sustainability-Related Content

Tables

Table 1: Life Cycle Analysis of LUT Moodle

Table 2: Journey map of Zohora

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

This research looks into the digital learning management system Moodle used at LUT University. Dougiamas (1998) created Moodle for teachers based on social constructionist teaching. Since the dramatic expansion of the Internet in the mid-1990s, more than a decade and a half have passed following the launch of Moodle and its infrastructure upgrade for different broadband network systems constantly enhancing our society (K. Nozawa 2011).

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, face-to-face learning became difficult as it was leading to widespread school closures affecting over 1.7 billion students worldwide (Alturki & Aldraiweesh, 2021). Universities quickly transitioned to online learning. The Learning Management System (LMS), a media integration for instructions that uses a single platform to organize communication processes throughout instructional events, is one of the technologies employed at COVID-19. LMSs are used as sustainability platforms by cutting-edge digital networks like Edmodo, Google Classroom, Forum, EdX, MOOC, and Coursera, as well as by specialized education (Warid, H., Musyarofah, L., & Taufik, K. S., 2023). Educational institutions started to focus on LMS, like Moodle, to facilitate remote education. E-learning has become a common and easy mode of learning. It needs User-Centred Design changes and some accessibility features to enhance its usability. Its technological evolution is likely to continue shaping and transforming the e-learning landscape. Students can now easily participate in a blended learning format.

As sustainability is a concern worldwide, the intersection of sustainability and digital education has garnered increasing attention in recent years. As educational technologies advance, incorporating sustainability into digital learning platforms is crucial. This paper explores recent research on sustainable digital education, including platforms such as Moodle. Moodle has so many look-active features. It has easy access and reliability. Moodle has already started including sustainability features, but there is still room for improvement by using user-centred design. This paper also explores how user-centred design (UCD) can help create better features for a more sustainable user experience. There are limitations in the research in this area.

1.2 Purpose of the Study

This study examines the user experience of LUT University's eLearning platform, Moodle, and how well it incorporates sustainability principles. The study will also propose a user-centred design approach for sustainable digital education to promote environmental awareness and encourage behaviour change. Moreover, this study is to encourage students to adopt more sustainable behaviours. By evaluating the current user experience in using Moodle, this research seeks to identify existing gaps and look into opportunities for further enhancement. This study also examines how effectively these ideas work in the existing LUT Moodle and proposes ways to enhance them. Finally, this study will look into improving the learning experience at Moodle and suggest ideas to encourage students to make sustainable choices in their studies and personal lives.

1.3 Structure of the Thesis

This study follows the logical structure of the research process. It begins with a brief introduction to this study. Next, it has the research questions, which serve as the foundation of this entire study. The research questions provide focus, direction, and purpose to this study. The literature study looks at previous research on Moodle, sustainability, digital education, and user-centred design for sustainability. This review aids in understanding current research and highlights the gaps that this study will address. Next, as a case study, this study explores the existing e-learning platform, Moodle, at LUT University. This section evaluates the existing LUT Moodle, the user-centred design feature of LUT Moodle, the sustainability assessment of LUT Moodle by assessing environmental, social, and economic impacts, and how these practices influence learning and behaviour. Life Cycle Analysis is also included to thoroughly understand sustainability within the platform.

Next, this study discusses the research methods used in surveys and interviews to gather information from LUT Moodle users. Next is ethical data collection, followed by data collection through surveys and interviews to ensure the research adheres to ethical standards.

After collecting the data, the thesis presents the results, which are both quantitative and qualitative data analyses, and a summary of the results. This section explains the findings and analyses the data.

The study carefully interprets the results, compares them with existing research, highlights their significance, acknowledges limitations and offers practical suggestions for future studies. The study then proposes a design towards sustainable digital education that would help motivate students to acquire sustainable values and develop sustainable habits. Its overall goal is to raise Moodle's awareness of sustainability. It also shows the implementation strategies and evaluation criteria using survey results and analysis with a summary.

In conclusion, the thesis offers a summary of the findings, emphasising the main insights and contributions of the research while discussing their implications.

Diagram 1: Structure of Thesis

2 Research Questions

1. In what ways are UCD and sustainability principles integrated into LUT Moodle?
2. How can LUT Moodle promote environmental awareness and encourage sustainable behaviours among learners?

3 Literature Review

3.1 Digital Education

Digital education offers an innovative approach to teaching and learning. Traditional educational experiences have shifted so much over time. It has improved educational experiences by using digital tools and modern technology. Integrating technology into the classroom can greatly improve how students engage with their learning (Parveen & Ramzan, 2024). Over the past few years, there has been a notable increase in the use of digital platforms and technologies in education, and after the COVID-19 pandemic, the trend has accelerated drastically. The global digital education market is expected to increase annual growth rate (CAGR) of 30.5% due to the rapid rise of educational technology, with the potential to reach \$77.23 billion by 2028 (Williamson, 2021; Williamson & Komljenovic, 2022; UNCTAD, 2021). So, this growth shows that traditional education behaviour is moving toward digital education. This shift to digital platforms gives students broader access to study resources with better learning outcomes, and they can think out of the box smartly. It also introduces new avenues for promoting environmental awareness and sustainable practices among students. When students understand sustainability more, they can think critically about it (Yan & Li, 2023).

As society moves toward a knowledge-based economy, where creative and intellectual abilities are valued more highly than tangible assets, this rise is consistent with that trend. This new world is defined by a different way of thinking, new interaction rules, and a dynamic information economy that operates across time and space. As the information and network economies intertwine, we see a transformation in how knowledge is valued and

shared, reflecting the principles of a new, dynamic economic model (Torrent Sellens, 2009; Powell & Snellman, 2004; Badillo & Bourgeois, 2014). Digital education works by encouraging people to create and share knowledge. This helps build more ideas and skills, making individuals and society more productive. Zou, Sun, and Zhou (2023) assert that education is essential to transitioning to a low-carbon, resource-efficient economy and call for tools and tactics that encourage sustainable behaviour.

Digital platforms facilitate flexible and creative learning experiences, which help students to think creatively, critically, and differently outside of the traditional classroom and textbooks. Nehru (1985) emphasised that technological advances require a shift in mindset—a change digital education fosters by promoting intellectual engagement and problem-solving skills. Digital technologies allow students to choose their progress at their own pace, promoting personalised learning (Zabiyeva et al., 2021). According to post-pandemic research, digital education helps achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by improving social fairness, productivity, and educational access (Burinskienė & Seržantė, 2022; El et al., 2020). Specifically, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development calls for high-quality, reliable data to support these goals, and digital education can play a critical role by offering efficient, interactive learning opportunities that reduce reliance on physical resources.

Digital learning brings environmental benefits in addition to personal ones. Online learning's adaptability enables students to access resources without needing physical materials, save money, and advance sustainability objectives. Digital assessment tools also help teachers because they reduce the time and resource requirements of traditional methods. By facilitating online classes and exams, digital platforms can help students and educators engage in environmentally friendly practices and reduce the ecological footprint of education.

Digital education is receiving more and more support from governments around the world. Since 2017, the European Investment Bank has invested over €1 billion in Finnish education to enhance access and quality education (European Investment Bank, n.d.). Azerbaijan's 'Program of Provision of General Education Schools with Information and Communication Technologies (2005–2007)' was funded to integrate digital resources into schools. As a result, it led to creating a digital archive accessible through the National Educational Portal

(Huseyn et al., 2023). The COVID-19 epidemic brought attention to the value of digital resources and demonstrated how digital platforms are now necessary for education delivery.

Creativity is essential from a technological innovation perspective, and digital education encourages innovative thinking and engagement (Meng, 2021). Digital education also includes various pedagogical applications, as described by Tondeur et al. (2008), who categorised digital tools into three primary functions: learning aids, sources of information, and operational technologies. Additional research by Pozo et al. (2021) examined how factors such as teaching experience and prior use of information and communication technology (ICT) influence digital tool utilisation in education. Digital platforms offer self-assessment and instant feedback opportunities, crucial elements of effective online learning environments (Bognár et al., 2021). He also shared an example that quizzes significantly impact students' attitudes toward learning and motivate them to succeed (Bognár et al., 2021). Parveen and Ramzan (2024) noted that engaging visuals and interactive tools play a key role in stimulating students' interest, making learning more dynamic and enjoyable.

Innovative digital educational methods can engage students in studying and encourage creative thinking. One effective tool for students is doodling (Aquino, 2013). It is a fun and creative way to visually express their concept understanding. It keeps learners engaged and helps them remember what they have learned. Studies show that doodling can improve memory, sharpen focus, and boost creativity, all essential for building strong independent learning skills.

It also gives learning a creative and individual touch, which enhances its enjoyment and significance. Aquino (2013) observed that students benefit from doodling as a method for organising ideas and improving cognitive abilities, with further support from Gupta (2016), who found that doodling enhances task performance and memory retention. In digital settings, these methods foster self-directed learning and critical thinking about sustainability, giving students the tools to engage meaningfully with environmental issues (Yan & Li, 2023).

3.2 Moodle

Moodle learning management system (LMS) is open source (Mushi, 2013). It was founded by Martin Dougiamas in 1998. It was officially launched with Version 1.0 in 2002. It was created to offer educators, administrators, and learners a secure, reliable, and integrated platform for building personalised learning environments. Moodle is essential in today's education, especially for e-learning. It has become popular worldwide because it is flexible, affordable, and focused on creating an inclusive and collaborative learning experience. It is now one of the most essential elements of the digital education landscape (Mushi, 2013). It can support most educational activities ranging from blended learning to fully online courses (Mushi, 2013). With over 410 million users across 242 countries and over 79,000 registered sites, including 7.2 million courses, it is currently one of the most popular LMS systems (Moodle Statistics, 2024).

A significant factor in Moodle's success is that it uses content management system architecture. It was developed using the open-source scripting language PHP. It follows a content management system (CMS) structure. It supports a variety of plugins, and as it is open source, it can be customised and allows extensive modifications. Due to its flexibility, Moodle has gained popularity in educational institutions. Through plugins, administrators and educators can choose tools for assignments, assessments, multimedia, and collaboration. Moodle has developed into a flexible platform that supports entirely online courses and blended learning, combining online and in-person instruction. This flexibility, along with its open-source GNU General Public License, lets institutions customise and share Moodle, making it an affordable and sustainable option for educational organisations worldwide (Dougiamas & Taylor, 2003).

According to research, Moodle's interactive, community-focused approach improves educational outcomes by raising student motivation, contentment, and engagement, particularly in STEM fields, where collaborative learning has proven highly effective (Gamage et al., 2022). Moodle's teaching philosophy is based on social constructivist principles. It is created with an educational philosophy that encourages peer involvement, active participation, and information exchange between students and teachers. It offers opportunities for personalised feedback and ongoing assessment. It helps

learners to study at their own pace and interact fully with the material, which aligns with constructivist and cognitive learning theories (Aulianda et al., 2023).

One of Moodle's standout features is its compatibility with Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI), a standard that allows seamless integration with third-party applications. This flexibility dramatically improves the platform's capacity to deliver an extensive and captivating educational experience. At institutions like LUT University, LTI integration has allowed Moodle to connect with specialised virtual learning environments, supporting smooth data transfer, simplified user management, and streamlined course enhancement (Nykänen, 2024; Lihavainen, 2019). Learning Tools Interoperability (LTI) lets educators add interactive tools and resources. These include simulations, external assessments, and multimedia content. LTI helps create a more engaging and varied learning experience. It also addresses different learning styles and subject needs.

Moodle has flexible customisation options to support traditional academic subjects, professional training, corporate environments, and other learning initiatives. Many organisations, including corporations and non-profits, have adopted Moodle for employee training, skill development, and compliance education. This flexibility allows Moodle to serve as a central digital platform for formal and informal education. It also facilitates a culture of ongoing development and knowledge sharing.

Moodle is popular due to its global reach and multilingual support. Moodle is available in over 82 languages (Moodle Statistics, 2024). Such accessibility makes it a suitable choice for diverse linguistic and cultural contexts. Moodle's community comprises diverse users, including K-12 schools, universities, governments, private institutions, and open education initiatives (Moodle Statistics, 2024). Due to its available functionalities, it has become a leader in the growing e-learning field.

Moodle continues to be relevant in technological innovations because of its open-source nature, which allows for ongoing development and customisation by users and developers worldwide. For example, Moodle's compatibility with new web technologies like HTML5 and responsive design has made it more accessible and user-friendly across devices. This compatibility ensures that the platform is mobile-friendly and works on different platforms. Mobile devices have become the most popular instruments for communication and textbook reading (Fojtik, 2015). Mobile learning is a fast-expanding field in educational research and

practice, spanning schools, colleges, universities, and workplaces (Kumar et al., 2011; Kukulska & Traxler, 2005). The capabilities of smart devices are also growing rapidly. These devices can support multimedia materials and other features, such as PDFs. Smart devices give users fast access to knowledge whenever they need it (Szyjewski & Fabisiak, 2018). Smart devices have become an essential part of people's lives, particularly at younger ages (Mihailidis, 2014). Smart gadgets are so attractive that they appear to be addictive over time (Goggin, 2012), and some people find it difficult to live without them. Educational institutions should adapt their teaching methods to incorporate mobile technologies, offering students a more comprehensive range of learning options (Fojtik, 2015). This adaptability is increasingly essential in the context of the rising popularity of digital learning, as it enhances accessibility to education for individuals across the globe. According to Nykänen J 2024, by supporting mobile learning, Moodle ensures that students and teachers can access their learning environments anytime, anywhere, enhancing flexibility and catering to a more connected, globalised student population.

Moodle's open-source model follows sustainable education by providing accessible, affordable, and unbiased learning opportunities for everyone. Open-source software like Moodle reduces dependency on costly proprietary systems, allowing educational institutions, especially those in resource-constrained environments, to implement and maintain high-quality digital learning infrastructure. Moodle's modular design also supports integrating sustainability-focused content and courses, encouraging students to engage with and learn about environmental and social responsibility within their learning environments (Nykänen, J., 2024).

3.3 Sustainability

The concept of sustainability came in the 1960s when people became concerned about the environmental damage caused by poor resource management. With time, as ecological issues have gained global attention, sustainability has also gained political attention. Established in 1960, the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) aimed to promote policies supporting sustainable economic growth, increasing employment, and improving living standards across member nations. By 1980, sustainability had become necessary in solving social and environmental problems. 'Sustainability' itself is a complex

concept considering various environmental, social, and economic aspects. In 1980, IUCN launched the World Conservation Strategy, highlighting poverty, population growth, social inequality, and unfair trade as the leading causes of habitat loss and environmental harm (Bluszcz, 2016). Sustainability is defined by the World Commission on Environment and Development (1987) as the ability to fulfil current demands without compromising the capacity of future generations to meet their own (Ray & Panigrahi, 2019). A significant milestone in sustainability came in 1987 when the United Nations Commission on Environment and Development released *Our Common Future*. This report defined "sustainable development" as development that "meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (WCED, 1987, p. 41). This definition highlights the need to meet current and future requirements. It also highlights the importance of ensuring fairness for future generations. It connects environmental issues with human, social, and economic systems, highlighting the interdependence of sustainability (Brown, 2011). The Brundtland Commission, the UN Conference on the Human Environment, and the Earth Summit 1992 were key events that made sustainability a global priority. Later summits, like the one in Johannesburg in 2002, promoted sustainable resource management and environmental protection worldwide. Sustainability addresses issues such as feeding a growing population, responding to disasters, and ensuring public health.

In recent years, sustainability has become essential in digital and educational fields. Kuppusamy (2019) suggests that green cloud architecture in e-learning solutions exemplifies "green computing," an approach designed to reduce environmental impact. Green cloud design includes using renewable energy, optimising resources, and implementing strategies to reduce the environmental impact of data centres (Radu, 2017). It also tries to increase cloud computing systems' energy efficiency and environmental sustainability. As digital education expands, sustainable practices like energy-efficient data centres and eco-friendly e-learning solutions show how digital resources can support sustainable development goals. By incorporating sustainability into digital education, students can learn about environmental issues and be encouraged to adopt sustainable behaviours through technology.

Moreover, education for sustainability (EFS) and sustainability in education (SIE) need to become regular parts of public-school programs and should also be included in college and

university courses (McFarlane & Ogazon, 2011). Learning about sustainability is critical because it helps us change our current way of thinking—a mindset that puts both our survival and the planet's health at risk (McFarlane & Ogazon, 2011). It feels like we are in a race against time to protect what remains undamaged and fix what we can regarding environmental harm (McFarlane & Ogazon, 2011).

In addition to policy and digital education, sustainability is becoming increasingly important in fields like product design. Bras (1997) identifies several factors that motivate organizations to adopt environmentally responsible practices. These include laws, customer demand, eco-labelling programs, and international standards like ISO 14000. Bras argues that effective, environmentally conscious design requires tools that are simple, cost-effective, transparent, objective, valid, robust, and improve understanding and prediction. These methods are critical for assessing and increasing sustainability in product design. Bras highlights that education is crucial in integrating environmental considerations into design. Training designers and engineers in sustainable practices can accelerate the development of environmentally friendly goods while encouraging innovative solutions in various sectors, including e-learning.

Incorporating sustainability into policy, digital education, and product design is essential to balance economic, social, and environmental goals. By addressing immediate human and environmental needs while prioritizing future well-being, sustainability supports a holistic approach to development, offering pathways to a more equitable and resource-conscious society.

Education is a significant sustainability challenge (McFarlane & Ogazon, 2011). This is a big part of the problem: our education has focused on economic growth and making money, not sustainability. Because we have been learning without considering sustainability and do not have a culture built around it, we now face problems that could have been avoided (McFarlane & Ogazon, 2011). Academic and non-academic institutions must work to educate and inform their members and organizational citizens about sustainability, one of the world's most significant issues in the twenty-first century (Lagos, 2011; Andrzejewski, 1996). According to UNESCO (2011), for sustainable development to work, communities need education, and the media should help people become informed and active citizens. Even people not in school can learn about global, regional, and local environmental, economic,

and social issues through media like radio and TV. People can also learn about sustainability from conversations with others and from observing everyday events and lifestyles.

3.4 User-Centred Design

The term "user-centred design" gained popularity through the work of Donald Norman, especially during his research at the University of California San Diego in the 1980s. It became widely recognised following the publication of the book "User-Centered System Design: New Perspectives on Human-Computer Interaction" by Norman and Draper in 1986 (Abrams et al., 2004). User-centred design (UCD) is important because it ensures that the products are created based on users' needs and preferences so they can be more accessible and enjoyable. UCD focuses on user needs and goals (Chammas et al., 2015). UCD helps design functional, engaging, and satisfying products for the user. At every step of the product development process, UCD aims to comprehend and satisfy the user's wants, preferences, and experiences. It ensures that it is intuitive and ensures the final product is easy to use and enjoyable (Brown, 2011).

Norman (1988) outlines four guiding principles for UCD:

1. Ease of determining possible actions
2. Visibility of system states and actions
3. Ease of evaluating the system's current state
4. Natural mapping between intentions and required actions

On the other hand, Meza (2008) emphasises that successful UCD integrates both usability and user experience (UX) into design. Usability primarily concerns how efficient and easy a product is to use. In contrast, user experience (UX) focuses on how the product makes people feel, its level of satisfaction, and its creativity and visual appeal. These elements are crucial to making products that work well and give users a desired, meaningful experience (Meza, 2008).

Jelsma and Knot (2002) proposed the idea of "scripting," which was one of the first uses of UCD in sustainability. Scripting involves designing product features that subtly guide user behaviour toward sustainable choices. For instance, Smit et al. (2002) demonstrated "user-

centred eco-design" in their development of a human-powered remote control. By creating goods that promote sustainable behaviour without sacrificing consumer acceptance, this strategy expanded eco-design from its technical roots into a user-oriented environment.

To encourage sustainable behaviour, Lilley et al. (2005) presented a framework for product-led interventions that fall into three categories: product-led, educational, and technical. Educational interventions aim to increase awareness by providing information, offering rewards, and applying penalties. Technological interventions aim to make products more energy efficient. Product-led interventions include (1) scripting, which guides users towards sustainable behaviour; (2) eco-feedback, where systems show users the environmental impact of their actions; and (3) intelligent products that automatically make sustainable decisions, such as activating energy-saving modes. The UCD process follows a cyclical design model (Roozenburg & Eekels, 1995) that includes stages of analysis, synthesis, simulation, and evaluation. When using UCD for sustainability, designers start by understanding how users behave and the environmental impact of their actions. They often do this by techniques like context mapping (Sleeswijk Visser et al., 2005) and contextual inquiry (Holtzblatt & Jones, 1993). Users play an active role in coming up with ideas and testing prototypes to make sure the product meets both usability and sustainability goals (Gyi et al., 2006). To improve the design and ensure that it functions properly in the practical process, users test these prototypes, which range from simple paper models to completely functional items.

Understanding human-product interaction and usability are critical enablers for sustainable UCD, helping to identify behaviours that lead to unintended environmental consequences and enabling designers to embed sustainability into products in ways that align with user needs (Pavelin et al., 2012). This method opens up new opportunities for eco-design techniques based on user-centred insights by extending sustainable design beyond material and technological considerations to encompass human behaviour, acceptance, and desirability.

UCD in sustainability not only improves the usability and appeal of eco-friendly products but also plays a crucial role in fostering sustainable user behaviours. UCD uses user feedback at each design step to create products that promote sustainable habits. This strategy promotes more general environmental objectives.

UCD can impact sustainable behaviour by creating goods that motivate consumers to make more ecologically friendly decisions. User-centred sustainable design solutions are designed to reduce the impacts by promoting sustainable consumption behaviours and energy efficiency (Wever et al., 2008). While traditional sustainable product design has focused on technical aspects, recent research highlights the importance of understanding user behaviour in supporting sustainability. More research is needed in this field, and further development is required due to insufficient collaboration between traditional sustainable product design and human-centred fields like user-centred design (UCD) and interaction design.

4 Research Methodology

In this study, the research methodology used a combination of a case study, surveys, interviews, and ethical data collection to assess the existing LUT Moodle's user-centred design and its sustainability behaviours and to understand how sustainability can be added to the platform. These methods include (1) a case study to analyse the current state of the platform and its features., (2) surveys to gather quantitative data on user experiences and interest in sustainability, (3) interviews with open-ended questions to collect qualitative insights from users, (4) mock-up propose sustainability-oriented features design based on the findings, (5) evaluating proposed design mock-ups through surveys and validate their effectiveness. These methods were chosen because they facilitate the collection of extensive information while protecting participant rights.

Diagram 2: Research Methodology

4.1 Case Study on Existing LUT Moodle

A case study was used in this research to closely look into the details of the current version of Moodle at LUT University. This study examined how LUT Moodle follows UCD and sustainability principles. It provided insights into LUT Moodle's strengths and limitations. This case study gathered practical insights that could contribute to the improvement of Moodle.

4.2 Surveys

In this study, an explanatory quantitative research method was chosen through two online surveys to collect feedback from students. The first survey was conducted to understand the experience regarding the existing LUT Moodle. The second survey was to get feedback about the newly designed prototype regarding sustainability awareness. These surveys

allowed this study to reach students who might not be physically available or have busy schedules. There were fixed questions with predefined answer options. These surveys made the survey look easy to complete and required minimal time for participants to answer. The surveys were anonymous to avoid bias and get honest feedback from respondents. There was no time limit for submitting it, which helped participants to think carefully about their answers. Participants found this procedure convenient, producing accurate data for the study.

4.2.1 Survey on Existing LUT Moodle:

The survey was conducted through online. A Google Form was used for the first survey to reach a wider audience. The form was a one-page survey with ten simple, straightforward questions. The answer format included Likert Scale response options such as a 1–5 rating scale, radio buttons for single-choice selections, and multiple-choice options. Participants could quickly complete and submit the form due to its straightforward design. The survey started on 1 September 2024 and continued until 15 September 2024.

4.2.2 Survey on Proposed Frameworks:

This survey was also conducted online. For this survey, a Google Form was also used to assess the effectiveness of the proposed sustainability features in the Moodle prototype. The survey focused on three main features: the "Doodle of the Day," sustainability quizzes, and reward badges. Participants were asked simple questions with limited options, such as "Yes/No/Maybe" and a 1–5 rating scale to measure their overall satisfaction. The survey gave a quick yet comprehensive assessment of how the proposed features might encourage users towards sustainability awareness. The survey started on 16 October 2024 and continued until 1 November 2024.

4.3 Interviews

This study used a semi-structured interview approach as part of a qualitative research methodology. The interviews were conducted online through the Microsoft Teams application. Those who attended the interview were asked some open-ended questions. It

gave them room to share their experiences. They shared valuable insights about Moodle's usability and their understanding of sustainability in education. Although the sample size was small, this method enhanced the survey by providing a deeper understanding of user needs and behaviours. This study conducted one-to-one interviews through online meetings with Microsoft Teams. Interviews were chosen as a data collection method to better understand students' experiences and expectations in the context of sustainable digital education.

There was a limitation in the number of participants, as only five individuals participated. Among them, one person was a bachelor's student, while the remaining four pursued master's degrees.

The author of the thesis hosted the interviews. The interviews were recorded for data analysis purposes. Each interview duration was between 10 to 15 minutes. The following participants were interviewed:

4.4 Ethical Data Collection

This study closely followed general research ethics principles during the data collection process. All participants participated voluntarily, and they were fully informed about this study.

4.4.1 Surveys

During the surveys, all the submitted data was anonymous. Participants were thoroughly informed about the purpose of the study. No personal information was collected.

4.4.2 Interviews

During the interviews, participants were thoroughly informed about the purpose of the study. With the participant's consent, interview sessions were recorded for data analysis.

5 Results

5.1 Case Study on Existing LUT Moodle

For the case study, this work explores LUT University's existing e-learning platform, LUT Moodle. It looks not only at facilities for academic engagement but also at finding how they support the university's broader commitment towards sustainability. The Key Facts and Figures 2023 report from LUT University states that there are 7,770 undergraduate and graduate students. As a result, many students use LUT Moodle. This e-learning platform offers a variety of synchronous and asynchronous learning opportunities for students. This flexibility is needed for working students or those living at a distance. It is helpful to reduce both time and financial costs and save economic benefits associated with travel.

LUT Moodle helps to reduce the environmental impact of traditional classrooms. Moving most interactions online reduces the need for printed materials and saves traditional paper study practices and other resources. The platform also has multimedia tools, making learning more interactive and diverse while reducing the need for energy-heavy physical spaces. With features like forums and messaging, Moodle allows students, faculty, and staff to collaborate. Using these features use can reduce the need for in-person meetings. These features support a more sustainable learning environment. This study will examine how well LUT Moodle follows sustainability principles and how it contributes to the university's goals.

5.1.1 User-Centred Design

5.1.1.1 Login Page

The LUT Moodle login interface is designed. It has a minimalistic and modern design. It presents the essential elements in a clean, uncluttered layout. The page header shows the logo of LUT University on the left side and LAB University of Applied Sciences on the

right, and different colour combinations provide immediate visual context and reinforce the institutional identity.

Figure 1: Login Page

The required input areas for the username and password are in the middle of the block. The input fields are easily distinguishable due to their consistent size and clear labels. The login button is also highlighted in contrasting colours to guide users directly toward the action. The website does not use distracting features. It allows visitors to focus on the task—logging into their accounts. Additionally, the password field is hidden with an asterisk sign for privacy. However, if a user wants to see what he or she is writing in that field, it can be seen by clicking the eye sign button and positioned so clearly at the end of the field at the right position.

Figure 2: 2-way verification

It requires minimal input and involves 2-way verification through the DUO app to enhance security. It gives streamlining access for users. For login from a new device or any unknown login, it gives a 2-minute time for the user to approve from the Duo application. Besides, when an incorrect username or password is entered, the system provides immediate feedback through a visible error message, prompting the user to correct their input.

However, the interface has no dark mode or accessibility feature. Eisfeld and Kristallovich (2020) explored dark mode as an emerging trend in user interface design. It is an important feature that should be on web pages. More people who use digital gadgets suffer from eye-related conditions as their screen time rises (Eisfeld & Kristallovich, 2020).

5.1.1.2 Dashboard Page

When a user successfully login to the Moodle platform, the Dashboard Page is displayed. It gives students an overview of academic activities, notifications, and course materials. This helps a user to keep track of their learning courses. The dashboard page has editable functionalities that give users access to customised sections based on priorities.

Figure 3: Dashboard

Dashboard Customization feature

The dashboard has an EDIT feature. It allows users to customise the dashboard to their preferences and needs. Users can customise their dashboard layout by adding blocks from the list of predefined blocks. This customisation flexibility in the dashboard is a UCD

feature of Moodle. It enables users to organise and prioritise content that supports their learning experience at best. From the predefined list, users can add the following blocks,

Figure 4: Blocks in Dashboard

Administration

This section gives quick access to administrative tasks. From here, instructors can quickly access administrative tasks.

Figure 5: Calendar Block

Calendar

A calendar block displays upcoming events, assignment deadlines, and quizzes. It gives students a visual, date-based organisation of their academic responsibilities.

Completion Progress

It shows a progress bar that visualises completed and pending tasks, which helps students track the completion of their course.

Figure 6: Completion Progress Block

Course Overview

Figure 7 : Course Overview Block

It summarises all the enrolled courses. Here is an overview of the course status with recent activities.

Courses

This is particularly useful for students and instructors handling several classes on the platform. This section displays a list of all courses that a user is enrolled in.

Tags

Figure 8: Tags Block

It displays tags related to specific courses or resources. It provides a quick way to find related content or topics.

Recently Accessed Items

Figure 9 : Recently accessed courses block

Here, it displays the user's most recently viewed content, which makes it easy to pick where it is left off in the study. This is a time-saver for students who frequently work on many modules or assignments.

Latest Badges

Figure 10 : Latest Badges

This block shows recently earned badges. This motivates students by recognising their achievements.

Other predefined blocks are available: Logged-in Users, Mentees, Navigation, Random Glossary Entries, Remote RSS Feeds, Starred Courses, and Text.

5.1.1.3 Course page

Course pages have a collapsible sidebar on the left side. Course instructors can customise a course as needed. For example, the CT30A8922 User Experience Design course is organised into primary sections: General Information, Teaching Events, Assignments, and Groups. Through the tabs and sidebar, the user can move to specific sections.

Figure 11: Course Page

A set of tabs in the centre of the page provides streamlined access to crucial course components: Course Overview, Participants, Grades, Download Centre, and Course Feedback. These tabs support a centralised view of course content, participant information, grading, resource downloads, and feedback channels, all within a single location.

Below the tabs, content blocks display each main section (such as General Information, Teaching events, Assignments, Groups, etc., pre-defined by the respective course instructor) in an expandable format. Users can click on each block to reveal detailed information without navigating away from the main course page. It makes it easier for students to access course content.

5.1.2 Sustainability Assessment

This study follows the fundamental principles of sustainability to examine the sustainable practices of existing LUT Moodle:

5.1.2.1 Environmental Impact

Reduction in Paper Usage

Paper production uses 40% of the world's industrial logging and is predicted to rise to 50% soon (The Paperless Project, 2014). With 35% of harvested trees being used to make paper, the amount of paper consumed worldwide has increased by 400% in the past 40 years (The Paperless Project, 2014). Over the past two decades, the amount of paper goods used has grown by 126%, from 92 million tons to 208 million (The Paperless Project, 2014). Specifically, it takes approximately 2.4 tons of wood to produce one ton of paper. However, using eLearning like Moodle has resulted in a massive reduction in paper usage. LUT University's administrative services have been nearly paperless since 2020 (LUT University, 2022). Most of its exams and other study materials are available through Moodle. Students can find study-related content available in Moodle. Moodle is increasingly replacing traditional paper materials, with PDFs now substituting for textbooks, reducing paper usage.

Energy Efficiency

For running a traditional classroom, it takes a good amount of electricity. Here in Finland, the weather changes drastically; a heater or air conditioner is usually required to keep a classroom comfortable. 99.5% of LUT's carbon footprint is caused by indirect emissions related to the university's activities. This scope also includes district heating and electricity in the property rent (LUT University, 2023). Online classes and e-learning platforms like Moodle work as a replacement for traditional classrooms to reduce energy usage.

Reduction in Commute

E-learning allows students and employees to study and take exams from home, so they do not need to travel. This reduces traffic and cuts down on carbon emissions. As a result, both the environment and travel costs are improved (Environmental Protection Agency, 2023).

Lower Carbon Emissions

Fewer people travelling to campus means fewer vehicles are used. As a result, there is low carbon emissions. Online learning has significantly reduced the carbon footprint compared to traditional classroom education. For instance, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) reports that each mile travelled to campus adds to carbon emissions, which e-learning helps to cut down (EPA, 2023).

Time Efficiency

E-learning removes the need for commuting, which leads to more flexible schedules and better productivity.

Resource Use

E-learning is more resource-efficient compared to traditional in-person education. It minimises the need for physical textbooks, paper, and other printed materials. Digital resources can replace these, saving trees and reducing waste. Educational institutions can save resources required to maintain physical buildings and facilities. There is less need for lighting, heating, and cooling classrooms and offices. Online resources can be shared among many users simultaneously without reproducing physical copies. This means fewer resources are used to produce and distribute educational materials. E-learning allows students to study at their own speed and according to their own schedules. This flexibility reduces the need for additional resources that might be used for traditional scheduling and classroom management.

5.1.2.2 Social Impact

An e-learning platform like Moodle gives remote access online to any student worldwide. Any international student can attend courses anywhere with only a mobile device. It gives access to more people and lets more students learn any course. However, Moodle does not have an accessibility feature for any disabled person. Through it, the students can save time, they can submit their works through online submissions, discussion in the forum, and the ability to access learning materials anytime. It gives them access to more people, and they can have more social connections. From surveys and interviews, it was found that students find it social and useful to use Moodle. Moreover, this platform provides diverse learning opportunities and equal access to every student.

5.1.2.3 Economic Impact

As Moodle is used in 155,268 sites with 426,019,232 users, it is a widely used platform (Moodle Statistics, 2024). So, its resources can be used from a central place. Centralised save much money for many sites, as they do not require hosting it manually or building new things from scratch. Only Finland has 358 sites; compared to the financial costs of running

the e-learning platform manual cloud services for individual institutions, the operational costs would be so much higher. So, Moodle saves money from traditional teaching and hosting and managing it manually.

Cost Savings

Students save money on travel expenses like fuel and public transport. Schools also save on costs related to maintaining and operating facilities.

Efficiency of Resource Allocation

Moodle has automated processes like grading, assignment submission, and communication as messaging through it. Those functionalities make it easy for the students to get course updates. Teachers can easily update the course materials, investigate the submitted documents, grade the courses, and give needed feedback. Also, with timely updates, Moodle has Turnitin plagiarism and an AI checker integrated with it, so it helps the faculty to check the originality of submitted assignments, and it saves a considerable amount of their time.

Scalability

Many students can join a single course through Moodle and access all its materials. As they can access everything without additional costs, it gives more scalability to a course.

5.1.3 Sustainability in Learning and Behaviour

LUT Moodle promotes independent learning. It allows students to monitor their course progress. Besides, it promotes continuous learning. A forum functionality encourages group work, knowledge sharing, and inclusive practices that leverage diversity and help sustain learning for all individuals.

5.1.4 Life Cycle Analysis (LCA)

This study analysed the platform's life cycle by comparing its environmental, social, economic, and sustainability impacts on learning and behaviour over time (including energy, materials, and travel reductions) with those of the traditional education system.

Table 1 : LCA of LUT Moodle

Sustainability principles		
Environmental impact	• Reduction in Paper Usage	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	• Energy efficiency	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduction in Commute 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less physical resources use 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Social impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time Savings 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More Engagement 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexibility 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equality 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Economic impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cost Savings 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency of Resource Allocation 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scalability 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Sustainability in learning and behaviour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable Awareness in Content 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficient study habits 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Travel reduction 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

By reducing paper usage, energy consumption, and the need for physical resources, LCA of LUT Moodle shows its positive impact towards sustainability. Additionally, it improves resource efficiency, flexibility, and user engagement.

5.1 Results from Quantitative Data Analysis

Thirty-five (35) individuals participated in the survey. They rated their experiences with LUT Moodle's design, usability and sustainability features.

Ease of Navigation and Usability

In the survey, the first question was, "How would you rate the overall ease of navigation and usability of LUT Moodle?" most respondents rated the platform positively. Specifically,

59% of respondents selected a rating of 4, and 20% rated it as a 5, indicating that most users found the platform user-friendly and easy to navigate.

How would you rate the overall ease of navigation and usability of LUT Moodle?
35 responses

Figure 26: Ease of Navigation and Usability (Survey)

Importance of Sustainability-Related Content

In response to "How important do you think it is for digital education platforms to include sustainability-related content?" participants strongly supported integrating sustainability themes. A combined 81% of respondents rated this as either "very important" (43.2%) or "extremely important" (37.8%), emphasising the perceived value of sustainability-focused content on educational platforms.

How important do you think it is for digital education platforms to include sustainability-related content?
35 responses

Figure 17: Importance of Sustainability-Related Content

Preferred Types of Sustainability-Related Content

When asked, "What type of sustainability-related content or features would you like to see added to LUT Moodle?", responses indicated a strong preference for varied content formats:

- ☑ 75.7% of respondents preferred "Videos and tutorials on sustainability practices."
- ☑ 70.3% favoured "Interactive quizzes."
- ☑ 67.6% selected "Case studies on environmental issues."
- ☑ 37.8% expressed interest in "Sustainability challenges (e.g., carbon footprint calculators)" and "Forums and discussion groups focused on sustainability."

What type of sustainability-related content or features would you like to see added to LUT Moodle?
35 responses

Figure 28: Preferred Types of Sustainability-Related Content

Likelihood to Adopt Sustainable Practices

In response to "How likely are you to adopt sustainable practices if LUT Moodle provided clear and interactive sustainability-related content?", the vast majority indicated a positive

inclination. 85.8% of respondents selected "very likely" or "likely," while 9.2% remained neutral.

How likely are you to adopt sustainable practices if LUT Moodle provided clear and interactive sustainability-related content?

35 responses

Figure 29: Likelihood to Adopt Sustainable Practices

Impact of a User-Friendly Design on Engagement

For the question "Do you think a more user-friendly design on Moodle would make you more likely to engage with sustainability-related content?", 80% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed, with 25.7% selecting "Agree." Another 14.3% held a neutral view, while the remaining respondents were inclined towards disagreement.

Do you think a more user-friendly design on Moodle would make you more likely to engage with sustainability-related content?

35 responses

Figure 30: Impact of a User-Friendly Design on Engagement

Interest in Sustainability-Related Content

For the sixth question, 'Would you like any sustainability-related content on LUT Moodle?'

There was a 'yes/no' answer, and 81,1% of respondents selected 'yes'.

Would you like any sustainability-related content on LUT Moodle?
37 responses

Figure 31: Interest in Sustainability-Related Content

Perceived Engagement Level with Sustainability-Related Content

In response to "How engaging would you find yourself with sustainability-related content on LUT Moodle?", more than half of respondents (over 50%) chose "Very engaging," while 34.3% selected "Engaging." A small percentage around (5%) were neutral, and the remaining respondents leaned towards less engagement.

How engaging do you find the current sustainability-related content on LUT Moodle?
35 responses

Figure 32: Perceived Engagement Level with Sustainability-Related Content

Challenges in using LUT Moodle

For the eighth question, 'What challenges have you faced when using LUT Moodle to access or engage with educational content?'

- ☑ 80 % noted a “Lack of engaging content.”
- ☑ 71.4% reported “Difficulty navigating the platform.”
- ☑ 62.9% cited “Slow performance/loading times.”
- ☑ 31.4% pointed to a “Lack of sustainability-related courses.”

What challenges have you faced when using LUT Moodle to access or engage with educational content?

35 responses

Figure 33: Challenges in using LUT Moodle

Importance of Sustainability Features in Concern of Usability

The next question is, 'How important are sustainability features to be easy to navigate and user-friendly?'. Here, 82,8% of respondents found it Extremely important. Moreover, around 10% found it Not necessary. Other respondents were neutral about it.

How important is it for sustainability features to be easy to navigate and user-friendly?

35 responses

Figure 34: Importance of Sustainability Features in Concern of Usability

Key Aspects of User-Centered Design for Sustainability-Related Content

In the last survey question, 'What do you think are the most important aspects of a user-centred design for sustainability-related content?'

Most of the respondents chose 'visually engaging content'. 82.9% chose 'clear instructions and explanations'. 71.4% of respondents expect easy navigation, 62.9% of people choose 'Interactively and participation', and 40% of respondents choose 'personalisation of content'.

What do you think are the most important aspects of a user-centered design for sustainability-related content?

35 responses

Figure 35: Key Aspects of UCD for Sustainability-Related Content

These findings show that users are interested in having LUT Moodle more interactive and engaging. Respondents would feel more engaged in having sustainability-focused, visually interesting content and user-friendly design features.

5.2 Results from Qualitative Data Analysis

Interviewee number 1 (date: 15 September 2024):

Interviewee 1 was a master's student in Software Engineering and Digital Transformation. He discussed its usefulness in managing assignments, exams, updates and notifications. He pointed out that UX should be modern and responsive. He thinks that if there are visual elements and sustainability-related topics, it can enhance student engagement towards sustainability. He finds Moodle promotes sustainability, as it gives him remote access to his studies and every study material he needs online. However, according to him, the user interface could be improved to make it more modern and responsive.

Interviewee number 2 (date: 16 September 2024):

Interviewee 2 was a master's student in Electrical Engineering. Overall, he expressed satisfaction with the Moodle platform. He also uses Moodle every day. He was happy with such a platform. He found it easy to use. He said he had never faced any challenges using it. He specifically praised the platform's ability to deliver notifications about assignments and exams. However, by adding educational materials about the environment and sustainability to the platform, Moodle could raise sustainability awareness.

Interviewee number 3 (date: 18 September 2024):

Interviewee 3, a master's student in Industrial Design Engineering, provided detailed feedback regarding his use of Moodle. He uses it regularly. He finds the LUT Moodle desktop web version is all right but needs more improvement. He thinks he got an email just before the deadline for any submission 1-2 hours ago, but he wants it to be notified 1-2 days ago. He mentioned that although the platform functions well on PCs, the mobile app needs to be updated and frequently has issues. According to interviewee 3, Moodle can incorporate sustainability elements like quizzes and instructional videos.

Interviewee number 4 (date: 19 September 2024):

Interviewee 4 was an undergraduate. He appreciated that Moodle helps him keep track of assignments. He also expressed interest in Moodle adopting sustainability-related features, such as quizzes or interactive activities that could encourage students to engage with environmental issues. However, he thinks Moodle should integrate with AI and have automatic evaluation features. He also found it took work to understand as a new user. He faced challenges to navigate through it.

Interviewee number 5 (date: 20 September 2024):

Interviewee 5 is another final-year master's student in Software Engineering and Digital Transformation. Besides his studies, he works as a teaching assistant. He provided similar feedback to Interviewee 1. However, he suggested that the UX should have a dark mood functionality, as it sometimes gets complicated for him to read in the traditional mood. He also thinks the mobile version should work better. He also suggested that the platform add accessibility features and follow eco-friendly practices.

Five people were interviewed for this study. The participants shared their insights about LUT Moodle. Participants found Moodle helpful, and they primarily responded positively about it. Some of the features they highlighted include managing assignments, scheduling exams, tracking deadlines, and receiving notifications. But they also indicated some problems they faced and suggested some improvements. Here are the points of the findings are as follows:

User Experience of Moodle:

Interviewee 2 expressed satisfaction with Moodle. However, others had mixed views. Interviewees 3 and 4 complained about the mobile app, including navigation issues and assignment submission problems due to bugs and design flaws. The third interviewee recommended making the mobile app better in order to improve usability. Interviewee 4, as a new user, needed help understanding Moodle. He asked to have some tutorials about using it. Interviewee 5 recommended implementing a dark mode feature and adding an accessibility feature.

Overall, participants suggested that a modern design would enhance user engagement.

Sustainability Awareness and Potential for Improvement:

Participants did not notice any direct sustainability-related content on LUT Moodle. The third and fifth interviewees suggested adding sustainability-related content to Moodle.

Overall, all participants suggested the importance of sustainability in education. They also expressed interest in visual features to promote sustainability awareness.

Notifications and Time Management:

Although the participants thought Moodle's notification system was good, one recommended that it should modify the timing of the notifications. According to the third interviewee, students should be given at least one- or two-days notification of deadlines so they can get ready.

AI and Automation:

The fourth interviewee suggested incorporating artificial intelligence (AI) and automated evaluation features into Moodle. He mentioned that it would help to get the grading in a better way and also improve UX. These comments show that some users anticipate that Moodle will have more advanced technology.

Suggestions for Enhancing User Engagement:

Participants suggested that Moodle could improve student engagement by adding more visual elements and sharing content on sustainability. Some participants pointed out that modern interface interviews can improve usability. Interviewee 5 suggested that integrating eco-friendly practices into coursework could enhance engagement.

5.3 Results from Proposed Design Data Analysis

This section analyses the second survey results based on the proposed design. It evaluates participants' feedback given on proposed sustainability features. Besides, the persona and journey map created for the imaginary character Zohora during the user-centred design process provided valuable insights. The survey with 22 participants focused on three main

features: the "Doodle of the Day" on the dashboard and individual course page, quizzes based on sustainability understandings, and the integration of badges as rewards for engagement. The critical evaluation criteria and analysis are as follows:

1. Engagement and interest in the "Doodle of the Day"

Survey Question: Do you think introducing "Doodle of the Day" in the dashboard would be engaging and interesting?

Results: Here, 80% of participants answered "Yes, " 15% answered "Maybe," and 5% answered "No."

Interpretation: Such a response showed that the "Doodle of the Day" was engaging. The positive responses suggest that the feature would capture student interest and motivate them to engage with sustainability content.

2. Likelihood of regular interaction with the "Doodle of the Day"

Survey Question: Would you likely interact with the "Doodle of the Day" regularly if it was available in your dashboard?

Results: Here, 59% answered "Yes, where " 23% answered "Maybe," and 18% answered "No."

Interpretation: While most would interact with the feature, the "Maybe" responses suggest that content quality or relevance may influence engagement frequency. This finding ties into Zohora's **journey map**.

3. Effectiveness of Quizzes in Testing Sustainability Concepts

Survey Question: Do you think the quiz can be an effective way to test your understanding of sustainability concepts?

Results: Here, 77% of participants answered "Yes," while 18% answered "Maybe," and only 5% answered "No."

Interpretation: The responses showed that participants were positive about it. This aligns with Zohora's journey map in the knowledge-testing stage, where she feels accomplished after completing quizzes.

4. Impact of Earning Badges on Future Interaction with Sustainability Features

Survey Question: Do you think earning badges would encourage you to interact more with sustainability features in the future?

Results: Here, 73% answered "Yes," 14% answered "Maybe," and 13% answered "No."

Interpretation: Most students believe earning badges would motivate them to engage with sustainability features. This is reflected in Zohora's **Reflection & Action** stage in the **journey map**, where she feels motivated by rewards such as points or badges. Badges are a tangible recognition of her effort and commitment to sustainability, which likely encourages her to continue interacting with sustainability-related content in the future.

5. Overall Satisfaction with These Features (Doodles, Quizzes, Badges)

Survey Question: Overall, how satisfied are you with these features (doodles, quizzes, badges) in this prototype?

Results: Here, 32% of respondents rated "Very Satisfied" (5), 41% rated "Satisfied" (4), 18% rated "Neutral" (3), and 9% rated lower.

Interpretation: The high level of satisfaction with the features indicates that students find the proposed design engaging and effective.

Integration of Personas and Journey Map in Evaluation

Zohora's persona and journey map were crucial in understanding how students might engage with the proposed features. The results from the survey show that Zohora's experiences, as mapped in the journey, align with the overall student responses:

Awareness and Exploration: The "Doodle of the Day" feature got students' attention. It aligned with the **Awareness** and **Exploration** stages in Zohora's journey.

Course Engagement and Knowledge Testing: In Zohora's **Course Engagement** and **Knowledge Testing** stages, the quizzes and course-specific doodles helped her connect sustainability to course content.

Reflection & Action: The journey map reflected the survey feedback on the importance of reward points and badges. These features motivated students, driving further engagement and encouraging behaviour change.

6 Discussion

The findings of this study provided some crucial insights into how effectively LUT Moodle can be used to promote sustainability-related content and boost student engagement. Based on the analysis of both qualitative and quantitative data showed common themes such as user perceptions of the sustainability content on Moodle, probable opportunities for its development, and design elements that could enhance student involvement. This study will interpret the findings with respect to existing literature, discuss their implications for the future design of Moodle, and figure out the possible directions for further research in the following sections.

6.1 Interpretation of Results

The LUT Module gained positive feedback for its navigation and usability from the students who participated in the survey and interview. Around 79% of participants rated Moodle's usability towards positive. It means Moodle's usability is good. It is important to maintain its usability so that students can focus on learning instead of dealing with technical issues. However, some participants acknowledged the necessity of visual and modern interfaces. One of the existing literatures suggests that the product design should be close to users' needs and preferences, which ensures the product is intuitive and satisfying to use (Brown, 2011). The findings of these interpretations suggest further improvements in the design, more specifically in mobile app functionalities, to meet user's expectations, as the core usability of Moodle is generally effective.

Concerning sustainability-related content, a large proportion of the students (81%) participating in the study emphasized integrating this type of content into digital learning platforms. This is in line with some of the existing literature that has marked education as one of the primary challenges to sustainability (McFarlane & Ogazon, 2011). This study found that the inclusion of a wide variety of multimedia content along with text-oriented materials in the Moodle feature will increase the users' overall understanding and participation in sustainability issues. The choice of interactive quizzes is consistent with the findings of other studies on the effectiveness of digital learning (Bognár et al., 2021).

Parveen and Ramzan (2024) state that using engaging visuals and interactive tools is crucial for capturing students' attention. They argue that this approach can make learning more dynamic and enjoyable, ultimately enhancing engagement and improving knowledge retention by making content more accessible. One interesting visual and engaging content is Doodle. Doodling content has been shown to increase motivation and improve learning outcomes by providing students with different ways to engage with and apply content (Aquino, 2013).

Another crucial observation of the study focused on the potential adoption of sustainable practices in the LUT Moodle. It brings to attention that the LUT Moodle should provide clear and interactive sustainability content. A significant 85.8% of respondents indicated that they would be more likely to engage in sustainable behaviour with access to such content.

6.2 Comparison with Existing Literature

There is much-existing literature about digital learning platforms, but few works about user-centric design and sustainable integration. The observations and insights of this study align with and further extend upon the existing ones.

The positive rating of the usability and navigability of the LUT Moodle platform (79% of students reporting a positive experience) reflects previous research findings that emphasize the important role of user-friendly digital environments in student engagement and retention (Brown, 2011). Moodle's effectiveness as a platform for academic content management is consistent in educational settings worldwide (Mushi, 2013). However, many of the respondents pointed fingers at the obsolete and erroneous features of mobile apps. This is similar to the common criticism in the existing literature about the requirements for continuous updates to maintain technological relevance and usability, especially with mobile interfaces (Dugiamus & Taylor, 2003). The suggestions for improving the user interface design reflect a growing agreement in the field that digital learning platforms should focus not just on functionality but also on creating visually appealing and responsive interfaces to enhance user engagement (Pozo et al., 2021).

Regarding sustainability integration, a predominant number of participants (81%) responded by choosing to incorporate sustainable content into the digital learning platform Moodle. It

resembles the findings of several other studies which focused on the significance of sustainable learning. McFarlane and Ogazon (2011) highlight the important role of education in addressing sustainability challenges, and studies of high demand for interactive content such as quizzes, videos, and case studies show that dynamic, multimedia-based content increases learning outcomes and engagement. This insight is validated by Bognár et al. and aligned with the work of 2021, who notes that interactive elements in digital learning platforms can improve student engagement and understanding, especially in complex topics such as sustainability.

In addition, many students (85.8%) said they would be more likely to adopt sustainable behaviours if they had access to clear and interactive content on sustainability. This supports the point made by El Masah and Mohieldeen (2020) that digital platforms can help raise students' awareness of environmental issues. Adding sustainability content to Moodle can inspire users to think and act sustainably. This shows a strong link between online learning and real-world sustainable actions.

Another important finding from this study is that user interface can influence engagement. A good portion of interviewees (78.4%) expressed support for a more user-friendly and visually appealing interface for Moodle. According to them such changes would enhance user engagement with Moodle. This concept aligns with some existing research on the critical role of user experience (UX) in educational technology (Gyi et al., 2006). In 2011, Brown stated that educational tools must meet users' expectations and create an engaging and useful learning experience.

These findings support previous research. They highlight Moodle's role in promoting sustainable learning. The study also shows how Moodle addresses student behaviour and how better design improves the learning process.

6.3 Implications of the Findings

Based on the results from this study, there were some practical recommendations for better design of Moodle. More interactive and visually appealing sustainable content can increase student engagement and, as a result, raise environmental awareness too.

Additionally, interactive and visually exciting content might encourage students to adopt sustainable behaviours. Including reward points might increase learning engagement and encourage learning.

Moreover, the results highlight the potential of Moodle to support the broader goal of promoting sustainability. Since many respondents are already learning about sustainability in their courses, adding sustainability features to Moodle can help extend this learning beyond the classroom, encouraging students to apply sustainable practices in their everyday lives.

6.4 Limitations of the Study

The findings provided helpful information, but the study has several limitations.

For initial research, the study used a survey size of 35 participants and an interview of only 5 participants; it was a small size, and it may not fully reflect the wide range of student experiences and preferences. Future research with a larger group of participants could provide a better understanding of how sustainability features are working.

Furthermore, self-reported data from surveys and interviews were used in this study, which could be biased by response. To get a better understanding of how the proposed features affect student behaviour, measuring student engagement, like examining Moodle's usage data, can be a good method.

6.5 Recommendations for Future Research

Future research can look into more extensive data collection with different types of users, including students of different backgrounds and teachers. It can focus on examining the effectiveness of different sustainability-related content in Moodle. For example, studies can look at how different types of content affect student's learning outcomes towards sustainability. Regular feedback collection from the users should also be important.

Additionally, further research could explore how the UX can be more UCD-focused. It can also analyse the long-term impact of sustainability-focused content on student behaviour. It

is also important to explore how users adopt sustainable behaviours in their personal and academic lives.

Finally, future studies can try to integrate advanced technologies like AI and adapt learning behaviour to personalise sustainability content and boost engagement. AI-powered features can be user-focused, and it can follow students' personal preferences and learning styles. It would make Moodle use more interesting and sustainable, making learning more accessible and engaging.

7 Proposed Design

The results showed that participants were interested in engaging with sustainability-related content. To achieve this, this study proposed an introduction of a 'Doodle of the day' story-based interactive feature in the dashboard and within courses. It would highlight posts related to sustainability that are relevant to the course content. Like a story, it can be brought up to students, as it is something new; students would click there and learn about it with a fascinating mind. This feature aims to capture students' attention by presenting sustainability topics fun and engagingly. Presenting the content as an interactive "story" would make students more likely to engage with it. It would help them understand sustainability concepts and encourage eco-friendly behaviours.

Additionally, a persona of the fictional character Zohora was created to show how a student might use the "Doodle of the Day" feature. Zohora's journey shows how this interesting and interactive approach can grab her interest, help her learn about sustainability only, and inspire her to use these ideas in real life.

Figure 12 : Proposed design plan

7.1 Components

1. Showcasing Sustainability-Related Doodles on The Dashboard

When a user logs in, a "Doodle of the Day" doodle story will appear on the dashboard. The doodle would be visually attractive and designed to capture the student's interest. Clicking on it would take you to the story it is about. If a student finds the topic interesting, they can click on the doodle to read about it. That doodle cover image would give an insight into sustainability practice and real-world applications. This feature would allow students to discover new sustainability topics in an engaging way and increase their environmental awareness.

Figure 13 : Proposed Dashboard

2. Doodle Stories Relevant to Course Content

When students enter a certain course, they will see a "Doodle Story" feature on the course website. These doodles will be filtered based on the course's subject matter and highlight sustainability practices relevant to the course material. For example, in a course on industrial design, the content would show a doodle about recycling initiatives. By checking over these stories, students can expand their knowledge. This feature would help students to have a good understanding of sustainability.

Figure 14 : Proposed course Dashboard

3. Quizzes for Reward Points

At the end of the course, students will have an opportunity to take a short quiz based on the sustainability-related doodles they interacted with during the course. The quiz would be designed to assess their understanding of the sustainability concepts presented. Based on the quiz results, the course instructor can reward them with points or credits upon completion. These quizzes can be either mandatory or optional. A student would only get a reward after successfully completing a quiz. This feature would motivate them to learn more deeply and retain the knowledge they have gained.

Figure 15 : Proposed Quiz

4. Special Recognition through Badges in the Student Profile

After successful completion of the quizzes, students will receive badges as rewards. It would keep encouraging them. Based on their performance, participants would receive reward badges. The rewards would provide special recognition and encourage students to participate actively.

Figure 16 : Proposed Badge reward

Implementing these design features in Moodle would give students a new way of learning. Through these enhancements, Moodle can be better positioned to promote environmental awareness and behaviour changes among students at LUT University.

7.2 Implementation Strategies

The "Doodle of the Day" feature looks to generate interesting content that promotes sustainability awareness. These doodles will appear on the dashboard and in courses, with rewards like points and badges to make learning more engaging. Student feedback will help improve the feature, while promotions and teacher training will ensure everyone knows how to use it. These steps aim to make learning about sustainability easy, enjoyable, and meaningful.

Persona of Zohora

Figure 17 : Persona of Zohora

Journey map of Zohora

Figure 18 : Journey map of Zohora

Table 2: Journey map of Zohora

Stage	Action	Touchpoints	Experience & Emotions	Challenges	Opportunities
1. Awareness	Zohora logs into Moodle and notices a “Sustainability Doodle” on the dashboard.	Dashboard screen doodle highlight.	Curious, slightly surprised. Finds it refreshing and engaging.	May skip over if the content isn’t interesting at a glance.	Use appealing visuals, engaging titles to capture her interest.
2. Exploration	She clicks on the doodle and reads a story about recent green tech trends.	Interactive Doodle Story popup	Intrigued; feels the content is relevant to her studies.	If text-heavy, she may feel overwhelmed and lose interest quickly.	Keep doodles concise with visual support, links for deeper dives.
3. Course Engagement	In her “Green Software Engineering” course, she sees a course-specific doodle about energy-efficient algorithms.	Click on the course dashboard Doodle	Finds the info highly relevant, sees practical applications.	Needs clarity on how doodles integrate with the course material.	Align doodles closely with course themes, add links to materials.

4. Knowledge Testing	After finishing a module, she takes a short quiz on sustainability concepts from the doodle.	Quiz feature in Moodle	Feels accomplished, enjoys earning points as a reward.	May lose interest, if the quizzes are too much difficult and challenging.	Interesting friendly quizzes for a smooth start.
5. Reflection & Action	After earning points, she reviews her learning and considers how to apply it in projects.	Reward points on final grades	Motivated by grades; feels invested in sustainability.	If the reward system lacks variety, she may lose interest.	Expand rewards to include badges.

8 Summary

This study looked at how Moodle implements UCD and follows sustainability concepts. It provided insights into LUT Moodle's strengths and some issues. This study gathered practical information and offered features to Moodle.

Moodle can incorporate and promote sustainability concepts to enhance student involvement. The proposed design features aimed to make the learning experience more engaging and accessible by introducing interactive and user-friendly features. These included a daily "Doodle of the Day" on the Moodle dashboard, unique "Doodle Stories" tied to each course, quizzes to test sustainability knowledge, and badges to recognise and reward students for actively participating in sustainability-related content.

The findings were based on a survey. The majority of students expressed positive interest in engaging with the "Doodle of the Day,". Most of them found it visually encouraging and motivating. Quizzes are designed to check sustainability knowledge, and rewards as badges are used as positive incentives. These features proved positive in motivating students to engage more with the content.

Further insights were drawn from the persona and journey map of a fictional character, Zohora. Her journey map showed the overall response to these elements. The positive feedback about the proposed features is clear. It indicates that students would like to engage with sustainability content. This happens when the content is presented in an interactive way. It is also important for the content to be interesting. The use of elements like quizzes, badges and rewards suggests that these features not only improve learning but also offer students tangible incentives to interact with and remember sustainability concepts. This could foster a greater sense of responsibility. It could also increase commitment to sustainable behaviours.

Moreover, the findings point out the positive response about aligning and adding sustainability-related content besides the course materials. Students expressed a preference for sustainability content that is interesting and related to course materials.

Although the suggested sustainability aspects were well appreciated, this study offers several chances for additional research to improve and enhance the design. One thing to look at is how it is affecting students' ability to get knowledge and their motivation towards sustainability with time. This would make it easier to assess if utilising Moodle's sustainability material can serve in the long run. As the current study focused on only a certain number of users of LUT University, for better understanding, it is important to try it in other institutions and check if it is widely applicable.

Finally, future studies could explore the impact of student engagement in more detail. Incorporating machine learning and AI to incorporate sustainability-based content based on individuals' interests can improve interaction and motivation. Future research should gather ongoing feedback to keep the sustainability features relevant, engaging, and effective. This iterative process could also involve A/B testing, user surveys, and user analytics to fine-tune the features and ensure success.

9 References

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Appendices

Appendix 1

The image shows a Google Form titled "LUT Moodle Towards Sustainable Digital Education" with the subtitle "Master's thesis data collection survey form". The form is designed for a user named "shah.k.wespin@gmail.com" and includes a "Not shared" indicator. A red asterisk indicates that the following questions are required.

Question 1: "How would you rate the overall ease of navigation and usability of LUT Moodle?" This is a Likert scale from 1 to 5, with "Very difficult" at 1 and "Very easy" at 5.

Question 2: "How important do you think it is for digital education platforms to include sustainability-related content?" This is a radio button question with options: "Extremely important", "Very important", "Moderately important", "Slightly important", and "Not important at all".

Question 3: "How likely are you to adopt sustainable practices if LUT Moodle provided clear and interactive sustainability-related content?" This is a radio button question with options: "Very likely", "Likely", "Neutral", "Unlikely", and "Very unlikely".

Question 4: "What type of sustainability-related content or features would you like to see added to LUT Moodle?" This is a checkbox question with options: "Interactive quizzes", "Videos and tutorials on sustainability practices", "Case studies on environmental issues", "Sustainability challenges (e.g., carbon footprint calculations)", "Forums and discussion groups focused on sustainability", and "Other (please specify)".

Question 5: "Do you think a more user-friendly design on Moodle would make you more likely to engage with sustainability-related content?" This is a radio button question with options: "Strongly agree", "Agree", "Neutral", "Disagree", and "Strongly disagree".

Question 6: "Have you encountered any sustainability-related content on LUT Moodle?" This is a radio button question with options: "Yes" and "No".

Question 7: "How engaging do you find the current sustainability-related content on LUT Moodle?" This is a radio button question with options: "Very engaging", "Engaging", "Neutral", "Not very engaging", and "Not engaging at all".

Question 8: "What challenges have you faced when using LUT Moodle to access or engage with educational content?" This is a checkbox question with options: "Difficulty navigating the platform", "Lack of engaging content", "Slow performance/loading times", "Lack of sustainability-related courses", and "Other".

Question 9: "How important is it for sustainability features to be easy to navigate and user-friendly?" This is a Likert scale from 1 to 5, with "Not important" at 1 and "Extremely important" at 5.

Question 10: "What do you think are the most important aspects of a user-centered design for sustainability-related content?" This is a checkbox question with options: "Easy navigation", "Clear instructions and explanations", "Visually engaging content", "Interactivity and participation", "Personalization of content", and "Other".

At the bottom of the form, there is a "Submit" button, a progress bar showing "Page 1 of 1", and a "Clear form" link. A footer note states: "Never submit passwords through Google Forms. This content will be visible to all users. Share | Report | Feedback | Settings | Privacy Policy". The Google Forms logo is also present.

Figure 19: Survey on Existing LUT Moodle

Appendix 2

Thesis topic: LUT Moodle Towards Sustainable Digital Education: Designing User-Centred Platforms for Environmental Awareness and Behaviour Change.

The following set of questions were asked during the interview session,

1. Can you please share your experience with LUT Moodle?
2. How user-friendly do you find LUT Moodle's current interface?
3. What do you know about the concept of sustainability in education?
4. What sustainability features have you found in LUT Moodle?
5. Are there any specific interactive elements (like quizzes, forums, or multimedia) that would make learning about sustainability more effective?
6. What features would you suggest enhancing the user experience and integrating sustainability principles into LUT Moodle?

Appendix 3

Survey on Evaluation of Sustainability Features in Moodle Prototype

Please rate your experience with the sustainability-related Doodle feature in the Moodle prototype on the following scale:

1 = Strongly Disagree
2 = Disagree
3 = Neutral
4 = Agree
5 = Strongly Agree

* indicates required question

Dashboard Prototype

1. Do you think, introducing "Doodle of the Day", in dashboard would be engaging and interesting? *

Yes
 No
 Maybe

2. Would you likely to interact with the "Doodle of the Day" regularly if it was available in your Dashboard. *

Yes
 No
 Maybe

Sustainability Quiz Prototype

3. Do you think, the quiz can be an effective way to test your understanding of sustainability concepts? *

Yes
 No
 Maybe

Badge Prototype

4. Do you think, earning badges would encourage you to interact more with sustainability features in the future? *

Yes
 No
 Maybe

5. Overall, your satisfaction with these features (doodles, quizzes, badges) in this prototype. *

1 2 3 4 5

☆ ☆ ☆ ☆ ☆

Figure 20: Survey on Proposed Design

Appendix 4

1. Do you think, introducing "Doodle of the Day", in dashboard would be engaging and interesting?
22 responses

Figure 21: Engagement and Interest in the "Doodle of the Day"

2. Would you likely to interact with the "Doodle of the Day" regularly if it was available in your Dashboard.
22 responses

Figure 22 : Likelihood of Regular Interaction with the "Doodle of the Day"

3. Do you think, the quiz can be an effective way to test your understanding of sustainability concepts?

22 responses

Figure 23 : Effectiveness of Quizzes in Testing Sustainability Concepts

4. Do you think, earning badges would encourage you to interact more with sustainability features in the future?

22 responses

Figure 24 ; Impact of Earning Badges on Future Interaction with Sustainability Features

5. Overall, yur satisfaction with these features (doodles, quizzes, badges) in this prototype.

22 responses

Figure 25 : Overall Satisfaction with These Features (Doodles, Quizzes, Badges)

Appendix 5

The GitHub repository links to the prototype page, <https://github.com/waqer/Masters-Thesis.git>

Appendix 6

Miro board link for Persona, <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVLLZT-xo=/>

Appendix 7

Miro board link for Journey map, <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVLHF5Q2o=/>